

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

SIR FITZROY MACLEAN – A BRITISH FRIEND OF GEORGIA

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Abstract

Georgian-British relations encompass many fascinating aspects. In this regard, the sibling duo of Oliver and Marjorie Wardrop stand out as colourful figures. Another significant and distinguished personality in the history of Georgian-British relations is Sir Fitzroy Maclean—a politician, diplomat, military officer, and historian—who is also considered a prototype for Ian Fleming's famous character, James Bond. Fitzroy Maclean's historiographical legacy covers various aspects of British history as he actively worked on key events of World War II and Russian history. Maclean's first encounter with Georgians occurred between 1934 and 1937 while working at the British Embassy in Paris. During this time, he met the renowned Mdivani family and even conducted a brief romantic relationship with one of its members, Rusudan (Rosy) Mdivani. In 1937, Maclean voluntarily transferred to the British Embassy in the Soviet Union. While in Moscow, he combined his diplomatic career with travel, exploring the Caucasus and Central Asia.

Fitzroy Maclean visited Georgia several times, first in 1937 and again in 1939. His observations and accounts serve as valuable historical sources, as foreign visitors faced significant restrictions on movement and communication within Soviet republics during the repressive 1930s. Maclean was one of the first British researchers to study Joseph Stalin's personality by delving into details of his childhood. He frequently visited Gori and other locations connected to Stalin's early life. During World War II, Fitzroy Maclean played an active role on the North African and Balkan fronts. He is also regarded as one of the founders of the renowned British special forces unit, the Special Air Service (SAS).

Keywords: Georgia, Great Britain, British-Georgian relations, Sir Fitzroy Maclean.

Introduction:

Georgian-British relations encompass many fascinating aspects. In this regard, the sibling duo of Oliver and Marjorie Wardrop stand out as colourful figures. Another significant and distinguished personality in the history of Georgian-British relations is Sir Fitzroy Maclean—a politician, diplomat, military officer, and historian—who is also considered a prototype for Ian Fleming's famous character, James Bond. Fitzroy Maclean's historiographical legacy covers various aspects of British history as he actively worked on key events of World War II and Russian history. Maclean's first encounter with Georgians occurred between 1934 and 1937 while working at the British Embassy in Paris. During this time, he met the renowned Mdivani family and even conducted a brief romantic relationship with one of its members, Rusudan (Rosy) Mdivani. In 1937, Maclean voluntarily transferred to the British Embassy in the Soviet Union. While in Moscow, he combined his diplomatic career with travel, exploring the Caucasus and Central Asia.

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regarded as one of the founders of the renowned British special forces unit, the Special Air Service (SAS).

Methods:

In the course of working on the paper, we employed an appropriate research methodology. To examine historical events in their temporal dynamics, we applied the principle of historicism, which enables us to observe the development of historical events from their inception and to discern their relationship to other processes. Since our principal sources consisted of memoir literature, which is characterised by subjectivity, we turned to scholarly works, press materials, and archival documents to corroborate and balance the historical processes and facts.

Outcomes:

In 1933, Fitzroy Maclean began working at the British Embassy in France. In Paris, he developed close ties with Russian emigres, and it was within this circle that he first met Georgians. As his biographer Frank McLynn notes, "From the outset Fitzroy felt a particular warmth toward the Georgians. He cheerfully recalled their aristocratic pretensions and would say that before the First World War every seventh Georgian was a prince or princess (meaning of noble birth)" (McLynn, 1992, p. 22). McLynn further remarks that it was there that Fitzroy encountered the first great love of his life, Rusudan (nicknamed Rusi), Mdivani. (McLynn, 1992, p. 22). Rusi and Fitzroy soon grew close, and she introduced him to her family; however, Fitzroy quickly realised her grasping attitude, perceiving that her aim was merely "to marry her brothers and sisters into wealthy

families” (McLynn, 1992, p. 23). Their relationship ended soon afterwards.

On 1 February 1924, Great Britain recognised the USSR and soon afterwards established trade, economic, and diplomatic relations with it. From 1934 to 1937, Fitzroy Maclean served at the British Embassy in Paris. As his memoirs reveal, the threat of an approaching war was already palpable in Europe with Germany’s growing strength: “In France, many were wondering whether they could rely on Russia (the USSR) for help in the coming conflict, and what form that help might take” (Maclean, 1949, p. 15).

Although he combined work with leisure while in Paris, Maclean himself noted that life there was still routine for him, and he “requested a transfer to the British Embassy in Moscow” (Maclean, 1949, p. 26). His decision surprised everyone, since “a posting to Moscow was considered the poorest assignment, owing to the harsh conditions—for example, at that time not a single woman worked at the British Embassy in Moscow” (Maclean, 1949, p. 26). He was appointed secretary at the British Embassy in Moscow: “At that time the embassy’s principal aim in Moscow was to address the question of the Soviet Union’s possible alliance in a future war with Germany” (Dooley, 2014, p. 32). As he recalls, everyone at the Foreign Office was astonished by his request, for no one had ever before expressed a personal wish to work in the USSR (Maclean, 1949, p. 17). His general knowledge of the Soviet Union was limited to scholarly literature, Russian émigrés, and Soviet films (Maclean, 1949, p. 17). He was also particularly interested in Central Asia: “for twenty years no foreign traveller had been there; the region had been closed even in the imperial era, and travel there was still impossible, especially for a British official” (Maclean, 1949, p. 17).

His first impressions on crossing the Soviet border are striking: “It was then that I first caught the smell that was to follow me for the next two and a half years. As earlier travellers had written, it was the ‘Russian smell’: black bread, vodka, sheepskin, and dirty clothes, with an added hint of petrol, disinfectant, and soap, and a slightly sour aroma that seemed to hang over the entire country. I noticed that same scent in later years whenever I was with Russians abroad, and it would carry me back to old memories” (Maclean, 1949, p. 19).

As a foreign diplomat, he was constantly under the surveillance of the People’s Commissariat for Internal Affairs, and as he himself notes: “In Moscow everything was different. We had contact only with a few employees of the Foreign Ministry, and even they were afraid to associate with us. We had virtually no contact with ordinary citizens, since even official dealings with a foreigner were dangerous for a Soviet citizen. Everything was controlled by the NKVD”¹ (Maclean, 1949, p. 22).

As already mentioned, Fitzroy Maclean arrived in the USSR in 1937, when Stalinist repressions had reached their peak, and he observed the ongoing events, including the trials of Nikolai Bukharin², Mikhail Tukhachevsky³, and others. He summed up his stay in the Soviet Union after several months as follows: “During

my time in Moscow, even under the highly isolated conditions in which we lived, I learned more about the Soviet Union in a few months than I could have from reading every book ever written on the subject” (Maclean, 1949, p. 29).

¹ *NKVD-The People’s Commissariat for international Affairs, abbreviated as NKVD, was the interior ministry and secret police of the Soviet Union from 1934 to 1946.*

² *Nikolai Bukharin (1888-1938)-Russian revolutionary, Soviet politician, and marxist theorist.*

³ *Mikhail Tukhachevsky (1893-1937)-nicknamed the Red Napoleon, was as Soviet general who was prominent between 1918 and 1937 as a military officer and theoretician.*

Fitzroy spent two years in the USSR, from 1937 to 1939, and recorded his impressions in his celebrated autobiographical work *Eastern Approaches*. His first plan was to visit Central Asia, a region closed to foreigners and a place of exile for the repressed. He was refused a train ticket from Moscow to Tashkent because a special permit was required. He also noted that the alternative route through Siberia to Novosibirsk was risky, since representatives of the People’s Commissariat for Internal Affairs inspected everyone. He therefore decided to travel to Baku and from there continue to Central Asia by the Caspian coastal railway, which was a legal route (Maclean, 1949, p. 30).

In Baku he visited the graves of British soldiers who had died fighting the Bolsheviks and also the “Monument to the 26 Baku Commissars,” who had been executed by British troops in 1918 year. Fitzroy Maclean arrived in Georgia in the spring of 1937, travelling by train from Baku to Tbilisi. He described the city as follows: “Tiflis has a southern charm and the power to impress. It is the best place for a holiday—I had never seen anything like it in the Soviet Union. In the old town, verandas and balconies are attached to the houses like birds’ nests” (Maclean, 1949, p. 45).

During his stay in Tbilisi, he lodged at the Grand Hotel, which at the time was considered a high-class establishment. He noted that his choice of accommodation was not accidental: “Fifty or sixty years ago, my grandfather (Alan Henry Maclean) also stayed in this hotel. The hotel met Soviet standards, offered good food, and had excellent wine in the cellar. (Maclean, 1949, p. 45).

His characterisation of the Georgians is particularly striking: “They are southerners and lovers of wine, highlanders and fighters. They combine the cheerfulness and vitality of Mediterranean peoples with the determination and courage of Scottish highlanders” (Maclean, 1949, p. 45). He decided to visit Tbilisi and locate the graves of British soldiers. To do so, he went to the local office of the People’s Commissariat for Foreign Affairs of the Soviet Union, where he met Leonid Stark, the former Soviet ambassador to Afghanistan, who was then working in Tbilisi. As Fitzroy Maclean recalls, during his time in Afghanistan, Stark “worked against British interests and organised anti-British uprisings in India” (Maclean, 1949, p. 47). Maclean

was informed that the locations of the British soldiers' graves were unknown.

Following this encounter, Fitzroy Maclean left Georgia and travelled to Russia via a military route¹. During the journey, he vividly described the scenery and route: "At Pasaunauri², we stopped above the pass for a meal—the food was astonishingly good. Freshly caught trout, skewered lamb, and red wine. The road became increasingly difficult, and from our high vantage point, we could see Mount Kazbek, a vast peak perpetually covered in snow" (Maclean, 1949, p. 51).

He summarised his first journey as follows: "My journey ended, although I was unable to travel to Central Asia. For the first time, I had visited the peoples of the East, lived among them, which proved a valuable experience and one I drew upon in the future" (Maclean, 1949, p. 51).

Fitzroy Maclean was one of the first British researchers to begin studying the early years of Joseph Stalin's life (Maclean, 1949, pp. 46–48). During his subsequent travels, he frequently visited the town of Gori. In the same book, he also provides readers with information about the Democratic Republic of Georgia³ and the 1924 anti-Soviet uprising⁴ (Maclean, 1949, p. 46). He prepared a special report on this journey for the Embassy, which was considered so important that it was sent confidentially to London. It was noted that the report contained particularly valuable information for them (Maclean, 1949, p. 54).

¹ *Via a military road or Georgian Military Road- is the historic name for a major route through the Caucasus from Georgia to Russia.*

² *Pasaunauri – is a small town in Georgia, situated in the Dusheti district, Mtskheta-Mtianeti region.*

³ *Democratic Republic of Georgia- was the first modern establishment of a republic of Georgia which existed from May 1918 to March 1921.*

⁴ *1924 anti-Soviet uprising – also "The August Uprising", was an unsuccessful insurrection against Soviet rule in the Georgian Soviet Socialist Republic from late August to early September 1924.*

In the spring of 1939, Fitzroy undertook another major journey, travelling from Central Asia to India, then on to Iraq and Persia. He finally crossed the Soviet border through Armenia, where NKVD officers escorted him back into Georgia. He travelled by train from Yerevan to Tbilisi and then proceeded to Batumi, as "I hoped to find a ship that would take me to Sochi, the main seaside resort of the Soviet privileged classes" (Maclean, 1949, p. 174). Due to a storm, he was unable to continue to Sochi, but he explored Batumi and its surrounding areas.

Fitzroy Maclean provided a vivid description of Adjara: "On the second day of our journey from Yerevan, we left the barren fields of the South Caucasus. I found myself among orange groves and tea and tobacco plantations, where hardworking men and lively children were at work" (Maclean, 1949, pp. 174–175). During his stay in Batumi, he visited a former Rothschild oil

refinery: "On its wall I encountered a large mosaic and a marble plaque in honour of Joseph Stalin, who had organised a major workers' strike there in 1903" (Maclean, 1949, p. 176). He described the hotel as follows: "I think the beef Stroganoff prepared by the chef was the best I have ever had. In general, the food here was the most delicious I tasted anywhere in the Soviet Union" (Maclean, 1949, p. 176). At the hotel, he met Ukrainian and Armenian collective farmers who were later sent to Gori and, "as I read in the newspaper, sent a particularly impressive telegram to Stalin" (Maclean, 1949, p. 176).

He then travelled back to Tbilisi, where he had first stayed eighteen months earlier. Aside from the new buildings, he observed that the general atmosphere of the city had changed, with an overall tightening of conditions. During his stay, as he himself notes, he inadvertently entered a restricted zone, where he was detained by the NKVD. While the situation was being clarified, he recalls: "I passed the time talking with the local officers about Marxism and the international situation" (Maclean, 1949, p. 176). After his documents were checked, he was released, and the following day Fitzroy Maclean returned to Moscow, again travelling via the Georgian Military Road.

From 1959 to 1970, Fitzroy Maclean served as Chairman of the Executive Council of the Britain–USSR Association, and from 1977 to 1987 he was the head of the same organisation (http://www.bewc.org/en/history_en.php 24.10.2025). Within the framework of this organisation, Maclean maintained close ties with the Soviet Union, which greatly facilitated his travels. Utilising his position and personal contacts, in 1958 Fitzroy Maclean travelled through Central Asia with the well-known English director and photographer Charles (Slim) Hewitt, visiting Samarkand and Bukhara. In 1959, they also filmed a documentary about Georgia — marking Maclean's first visit to the country since the Second World War (McLynn, 1992, p. 332).

Fitzroy Maclean's 1961 visit to Georgia was especially notable. He was accompanied by his wife, Veronica, as well as the British Ambassador to the USSR, Sir Humphrey Trevelyan, his wife Violeta, and several embassy staff members. Veronica Maclean's memoirs provide vivid details of this journey: "We visited Georgia once more, a place to which we often return. For me, it was not merely enjoyment. It was the warmth of the people and their hospitality, the ancient history, the monuments of the past. I took numerous photographs for Fitzroy's forthcoming book." (Maclean, 2002, p. 301).

The guests stayed at the Intourist Hotel, from where they travelled to Mtskheta to see the Jvari Monastery¹: "Jvari is one of Fitzroy's favourite churches, which he particularly enjoyed photographing. It stands on the summit of a hill and is an example of Georgian architectural genius." (Maclean, 2002, p. 303).

Fitzroy expressed his gratitude for the Georgians' exceptional hospitality by reciprocating many years later. In 1979, during the Georgian Culture Days in Glasgow, "Robert Sturua, Ramaz Chkhikvadze, and the State Dance Ensemble arrived in two buses as our guests.

¹ *Jvari Monastery-is a sixth-century Georgian Orthodox monastery near Mtshkheta, eastern Georgia, During a picnic, Ramaz and Fitzroy even went for a swim together in the river.*” (Maclean, 2002, p. 304).

Fitzroy Maclean, together with his wife, visited Georgia again in 1974. This journey proved particularly significant and fruitful, for it was then that he gathered part of the material for his future book, *To Caucasus: The End of all the Earth*. The work is divided into two main parts: the first is devoted to the history of the Caucasus from ancient times up to the first half of the twentieth century, while the second recounts the author's and his wife's subsequent travels in the region. Comprising sixteen chapters, the book highlights key episodes in the history of the Caucasus, with special emphasis on Georgia. Maclean demonstrates both a deep knowledge of historical sources and a keen ability to analyse processes. The book is richly illustrated with colour photographs by Veronica Maclean, capturing not only historical monuments but also ordinary Georgian citizens. Although written in a popular-scientific style, the work reveals the author's consistently positive attitude towards Georgia and its people. For the English-speaking readership, it served as an important guide for studying Georgia, from antiquity and the Middle Ages through to the 1970s.

This journey was indeed an intensive one, as Fitzroy and Veronica Macleans travelled widely across Georgia, visiting different regions, exploring historical monuments, and meeting local people. In Tbilisi, they toured the old districts and attended a performance of the Sukhishvili dance ensemble (Maclean, 1976, pp. 128–131). In this context, Maclean also reflected on the tragic events of 9 March 1956¹ (Maclean, 1976, p. 131). They visited the National Gallery and the Mtatsminda Pantheon (Maclean, 1976, pp. 132–133). From Tbilisi, the couple travelled to Kakheti, where they explored the Chavchavadze estate in Tsinandali. Maclean provides the reader with valuable insights into the work of Prince Alexander

¹ *The tragic events of 9 March 1956 – 100 people had been killed, with later investigations by the Georgian authorities that at least 21 people were killed and 55 wounded, mostly students and young people.*

Chavchavadze¹ and the role of his family in the development of Georgian culture (Maclean, 1976, pp. 137–138). They then visited Telavi and the palace of King Erekle II², as well as the monasteries of Ikalto and Alaverdi, each described in detail. Particularly engaging is Maclean's discussion of the Georgian “supra” (feast) and the unique phenomenon of the “tamada” (toastmaster) (Maclean, 1976, pp. 139–140). As previously noted, Maclean was among the first British researchers to take an interest in Stalin's childhood and frequently visited Gori. On this trip, too, they toured the Stalin House-Museum, the fortress of Gori, and Ateni Sioni (Maclean, 1976, pp. 140–141). In southern Georgia, they visited

Akhaltsikhe and Vardzia (Maclean, 1976, pp. 141–143). Maclean also expressed particular interest in Kutaisi, where they saw Bagrati Cathedral, Gelati Monastery, and the local museum. He also provided readers with important notes on the life and reign of King David the Builder (Maclean, 1976, pp. 143–145). After completing their travels, the Macleans returned to Moscow overland, stopping once more in Mtskheta. The Georgian highlands and the Georgian Military Road remained among Fitzroy's favourite routes, and as in earlier journeys, he offered vivid and detailed descriptions of the landscape and people he encountered (Maclean, 1976, pp. 148–149).

In September 1990, Fitzroy Maclean and his wife Veronica, together with their friends Lawrence Kelly and his wife, as well as Alexandra Hamilton and her mother, Gina, a descendant of the Romanov dynasty, visited Georgia (Maclean, 2002, p. 352). They were hosted by Gela Charkviani, who in his memoir *A Parade of Familiar Chimaeras*, provides interesting details about this visit. Gela Charkviani, together with his son Irakli³ and friends Otar Tsereteli and Givi Khomeriki, took the guests to Svaneti.

¹ *Prince Alexander Chavchavadze-was a Georgian poet, public benefactor and military figure.*

² *King Erekle II – was the king of the Kingdom of Kakheti from 1744 to 1762, and of the Kingdom of Kakheti from 1772 until his death in 1798.*

³ *Irakli Charkviani- was a Georgian musician, poet and prose writer.*

During their stay in Georgia, Gela Charkviani also took the guests to Likani, the former Romanov residence, and as he recalls, this visit proved particularly emotional for Alexandra Hamilton, being herself a descendant of the Romanovs (Charkviani, 2016, p. 293).

The year 1995 proved to be significant for the strengthening of Georgian-British relations. In February of that year, the Head of State of Georgia, Eduard Shevardnadze, paid an official visit to the United Kingdom, during which he met with Queen Elizabeth II, Prime Minister John Major, Foreign Secretary Douglas Hurd, the President of the Confederation of British Industry Lord Fairfax, Fitzroy Maclean, and others. He also visited the Bank of England and the Royal Institute of International Affairs (Chatham House). (Charkviani, 2016, p. 194).

Overall, Eduard Shevardnadze's visit to Britain was deemed a success: “Of particular note is the declaration which recorded the aspiration of the Georgian and British peoples towards friendship. The parties reaffirm their commitment to the principle of the inviolability of borders. The declaration emphasises that the participants support the peaceful settlement of all conflicts” (Georgian Times, 1995, pp. 1–2). The central topic of the visit, however, remained the issue of transporting Azerbaijani oil through Georgian territory, regarding which the Georgian side was conducting negotiations with British Petroleum (Resonansi, 1995, p. 1).

Gela Charkviani recalls the meeting between Fitzroy Maclean and Eduard Shevardnadze during the latter's official visit, at a luncheon held on the occasion of Shevardnadze's meeting with British Prime Minister John Major:

"My elder friend, Sir Fitzroy Maclean, was present. It was his biography and qualities that Ian Fleming had drawn upon in creating his immortal hero, James Bond. By then, Fitzroy was walking with the help of two sticks. He confided to me that his arthritis dated back to his youth, when he had made parachute jumps. This was when he founded the SAS – the Special Air Service – which fought in North Africa against Field Marshal Erwin Rommel, and later assisted Josip Broz Tito's partisans, thereby sparing Yugoslavia from Soviet domination. He had served as Deputy Minister of War, Member of Parliament, and was a fine writer, and had a deep affection for Georgia. I felt a familial bond with him; I thought of him as my uncle. I promised him that I would arrange a meeting with Shevardnadze that evening at the hotel – and so I did." (Charkviani, 2016, pp. 193–194).

In November 1995, Sir Fitzroy Maclean visited Georgia for the last time. On 13 November, together with the British Ambassador Steve Nash, he met with the President of Georgia, Eduard Shevardnadze.

Eduard Shevardnadze received the Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the United Kingdom to Georgia, Steven Nash, who was accompanied by a figure widely known in Britain – the writer, diplomat and military man, Sir Fitzroy Maclean, a great friend of Georgia and the author of numerous books and publications about the Caucasus, particularly about Georgia. The guests congratulated President Shevardnadze on his victory in the presidential elections of the Republic of Georgia and expressed the hope that in the near future Georgia would become one of the strongest states, since at its helm stood a figure of global stature such as Eduard Shevardnadze. Sir Fitzroy Maclean noted that he was writing a new book on Georgia, which would reflect both the country's problems and the progress it had made. (*Sakartvelos Respublika*, 1995, p. 1). Eduard Shevardnadze and his guests discussed pressing issues facing both the world and Georgia, with particular attention devoted to the problem of terrorism, which, in their view, ought to be resolved through the concerted efforts of international organisations. (*Sakartvelos Respublika*, 1995, p. 1)

On 15 June 1995, while swimming in a friend's pool, Sir Fitzroy Maclean — a great friend of Georgia — passed away. As Gela Charkviani recalls:

"It must have been midday on the 18th when Peter Naismith phoned me from London: I have bad news — Fitzroy Maclean has died. Unwittingly, I blurted out, I never thought this would ever happen. Indeed, in my imagination Fitzroy was a mountain somewhere in Scotland, forever standing, shrouded in mist; yet at times taking on human form and visiting Georgia, which he fell in love with at first sight — something so vividly felt in his book, now a classic. Later, the British Embassy sent me the obituary published in *The Times*. Slowly, from the fax machine emerged his brow, then his aquiline nose... I felt a strange dissonance: how grotesquely out of place high technology seemed when set

against so old and conservative a notion as death." (Charkviani, 2016, pp. 283–284)

He also notes that obituaries on Fitzroy Maclean's death appeared in all the major British newspapers. Each of them stressed that it was precisely Maclean's character traits and extraordinary life that Ian Fleming had drawn upon in shaping the figure of Agent 007. One obituary was even headlined: "The Real James Bond Died Today" (*The Independent*, 1995, p. 15).

Gela Charkviani wrote a letter of condolence, on behalf of President Eduard Shevardnadze, to Fitzroy's widow, Veronica Fraser, which he concluded with the words: "The Georgian people will remember with gratitude the handsome and proud Scotsman who bestowed upon their homeland the gift of selfless love." (Charkviani, 2016, pp. 283–284). He also drafted an obituary which was sent to Archil Gogelia to be read out on television (Charkviani, 2016, pp. 283–284).

The Embassy of Georgia to the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland paid tribute to the memory of Fitzroy Maclean and organised corresponding commemorative events. Ambassador Teimuraz Mamatsashvili sent a letter of condolence to the Maclean family on behalf of the Georgian people: "This is not only the loss of an extraordinary person and great personality, but also of the Georgian nation as a whole. The attention and care that Sir Fitzroy showed towards our country over the years will never be forgotten, and his passing is deeply mourned by every citizen of Georgia." (SUICA, Fund No. 1206, Inventory No. 6, File No. 56, p. 4).

Veronica Maclean sent a letter of thanks to the Georgian Ambassador: "My deepest thanks for your warm condolences on the passing of my husband. The sympathy expressed by his Georgian friends is particularly meaningful to me and to our entire family. He loved Georgia so much and had been eagerly looking forward to returning in the autumn with me. Fortunately, he did not suffer long, passing suddenly from this world. May the soil of his beloved country be light upon him. On 25 September at 12:00, a memorial service for Fitzroy Maclean will be held at St. George's Church, Hanover Square, London. I would be very pleased to see my husband's Georgian friends there on this day. With great respect, Veronica Maclean." (SUICA, Fund No. 1206, Inventory No. 6, File No. 56, pp. 5–6).

Ambassador Teimuraz Mamatsashvili submitted a report on the commemorative events to the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Georgia, Irakli Menagarishvili. (SUICA, Fund No. 1206, Inventory No. 6, File No. 56, p. 1)

Conclusion

In the present study, we examined a fascinating aspect of the multifaceted life of the renowned British political and military figure, Sir Fitzroy Maclean: his remarkable relationship with Georgia. Maclean acted as both a promoter of Georgian history and a true friend of the country. Notably, he first visited Georgia in the 1930s, during the era of Stalinist repressions, at a time when Western society had very limited knowledge about the country. He left behind valuable observations regarding the situation at that time. Through his books

and articles, Maclean introduced British society to Georgia and its people, highlighting both its historical past and contemporary life. Over the course of six decades, he visited Georgia in nearly every decade, preserving photographic material and providing vivid descriptions of both historical monuments and members of society.

Maclean also reflected on Georgia's future. In his view, an independent Georgia should serve as the centre of the Caucasus and a Christian state, governed by a monarchical system (Maclean, 1992, p. 352). His profound attachment to Georgia, however, drew criticism from the well-known French Caucasologist Robert Chenciner, who was more focused on the North Caucasus and Islamic regions (Maclean, 1992, p. 352).

Maclean's profound attachment to Georgia was also highlighted in his obituary published in *The Times*: "Throughout the Cold War, he regularly returned to the USSR, maintaining close contacts and visiting places that most Westerners would never see. His favourite place was Georgia" (*The Times*, 1996, p. 21).

Interestingly, his biographer Frank Maclean notes that "Fitzroy Maclean's travels to Russia (the Soviet Union) can be divided into four categories: 1. journeys undertaken for filming or gathering material for his books; 2. less frequent trips to explore places unfamiliar to him; 3. visits prompted by the British authorities to study the situation in the USSR; 4. the true and happiest journeys, when he went to his beloved Georgia" (McLyn, 1992, p. 350).

As already noted, Fitzroy, as a Scotsman, had a special regard for the mountain peoples. Georgia was remarkable to him for its mountains: "Fitzroy advised his compatriots that SAS training should be conducted in the mountains of Georgia" (McLyn, 1992, p. 359).

It is known that Fitzroy Maclean was present in the Balkans during the Second World War, with Josip Broz Tito and his partisans. Later, in the late 1980s, following the escalation of the Yugoslav conflicts, he relocated there with his wife to the Croatian island of Korčula, also assisting those affected by the conflict. When his biographer asked him, "There are mountains in Montenegro too, so why do you particularly like the Georgians?" he replied, "The Georgians are a sensitive, romantic, and nostalgic people, tied to traditional order and hierarchy" (McLyn, 1992, p. 350).

Interestingly, Fitzroy Maclean's favourite drink was also vodka, just like James Bond's. Notably, in one of the James Bond films, *The Living Daylights*, Bond's partner is played by Mariam d'Abo, the granddaughter of the Georgian general Giorgi Kvinitadze (<https://www.007.com/maryam-dabo-on-the-living-daylights>)

Fitzroy Maclean's life and work continue to attract scholarly attention, reflecting his enduring influence. For instance, British researcher James Kittson's publication, *Exploring Stabilisation in Eurasia – A Fitzroy Maclean Approach*, is particularly noteworthy. Kittson,

like Maclean, integrates military and civilian perspectives in his analysis. He retraces Maclean's path, travelling through regions of ethnic conflict such as the Caucasus and Central Asia, as well as Afghanistan and China. The work examines Maclean's activities, including his special relationship with Georgia, while simultaneously presenting Kittson's own approaches to conflict resolution in these regions.

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